

The Antecedents and Effects of E-value Perception on Consumers' Experience Of Digital Banking in Kuwait

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- **Executive Summary**

The main aim of this research is to investigate the antecedents and effects of e-value perception on consumers' experience of e-banking in Kuwait. A convenience sample of 569 e-banking customers is drawn from the ten major retail banks in Kuwait through online surveys. The current research investigated the following variables: customers' perception of E-banking Website/App Design, User Image, Security, Easiness of Use, Controllability, Interactivity, Attractiveness, Convenience, Personalization, Responsiveness, Service Quality, Availability, Information Value, Utilitarian Value, Hedonic (Entertainment) Value and Customer Experience.

The findings indicated that the overall perception of the aforementioned variables by customers in Kuwait is predominantly positive. Data analysis also revealed that the variables of this study are all correlated and have reciprocal effects on each other. Data analysis have also identified the major driving factors, or independent variables, that exerted a major effect on customers' evaluation of each variable of the study as well as the ability, of these variables to explain the changes in the values of the dependent variable.

This study has built a model that explains the antecedents and effects of E-banking value perception and customers' experience. According to this model, customers' perception of E-banking Value can be identified through three types of perceived value: Information, Utilitarian and Hedonic (Entertainment) Value. Customers' perceptions of the three types of Value, along with the perception of Service Quality, are all responsible for creating customers' E-banking Experience.

The findings revealed low importance of customers' demographics on the variables of the study. The findings also indicated no significant effect of customers' commitment to their banks, or usage rate of their E-banking services, on their evaluation of the variable of the study. Nevertheless, e-banking mobile users had significantly more positive perceptions of the variables of the study than e-banking websites users. In light of the above findings, the current study has adopted some recommendations to enhance customers' e-banking experience and value perception as well as enhancing the retail banking performance in Kuwait.

- **Research Authorship:**

This research is authored by Dr. Ahmad Khaldi, under a research grant from Kuwait Banking Association KBA. Dr. Khaldi has a Ph.D. in Marketing from the UK. He currently works at the Australian College of Kuwait ACK. He has a wide multi-cultural teaching experience for more than 19 years in British, Australian and Middle Eastern universities. He has previously served in many academic administrative positions including head of marketing department and vice dean for academic affairs in several universities. He has many publications in international peer reviewed academic journals. His research interests are within the areas of consumer behaviour, cross cultural comparative studies, promotion and advertising management, digital marketing and CRM. Dr. Khaldi is also involved in vocational and corporate training and has authored several vocational and training programs in Australia and the Middle East. Dr. Khaldi can be reached by email at a.khaldi@ack.edu.kw or ahm_kh@yahoo.com